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Introducing business and policy aspects to 5G and 6G

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Petri Ahokangas, Marja Matinmikko-Blue, Seppo Yrjölä
University of Oulu

Today's fourth generation of mobile connectivity services (4G) are available everywhere, and adoption of fifth generation (5G) networks is well underway. Compared to 4G, 5G has already brought about new business opportunities and enabled seamless virtual and augmented reality services, but also raised serious concerns on data privacy and security and the use of artificial intelligence. The sixth generation (6G) networks are already in R&D phase aiming at deployment in 2030. We need to understand today what 5G evolution and 6G may bring for the future of service delivery and how they will influence us. This edited volume from the world's first 6G research program at the University of Oulu, Finland, provides a multi-disciplinary and insightful overview of the subject, with contributions from experts in the field.

The contributions answer what 5G, its evolution, and 6G will be about; what kind of impacts 5G and 6G will have on future digital services, businesses, and society; how we could benefit from 5G and 6G innovations; and how 5G and 6G should be regulated in the future. Future 5G evolution and 6G are not only about moving toward faster, better, and more secure networks providing the basis for innovative digital services, they are also going to bring about a huge digital disruption that will affect all levels of society. This book will be of great interest to academics and students of management, telecommunications and digital innovation, as well practitioners and policymakers looking to the future of business.

This is an open access book.

Petri Ahokangas is Professor of Future Digital Business at Martti Ahtisaari Institute, Oulu Business School, Finland. Prior to his academic career, he worked in the telecoms/software industry. His research is in the intersection of entrepreneurship, strategic management, international business, futures research and action research in various fields on emerging technology. He has published over 200 scientific articles and book chapters on the subjects of telecoms, entrepreneurship, and internationalization.

Annabeth Aagaard is Professor of Digitalisation at Department of Management at Aarhus University, Denmark and the founder of Interdisciplinary Center for Digital Business Development. Her research is centered on digital and sustainable business development, ecosystems, and innovation management and she has authored sixteen textbooks and over 200 scientific and public papers on these topics. Furthermore, she is heavily involved in research projects sponsored by industrial foundations and acts as a strategic advisor to industry on digital and sustainable topics.

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The Changing World of Mobile Communications
Edited by Petri Ahokangas · Annabeth Aagaard

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The Changing World of Mobile Communications

5G, 6G and the Future of Digital Services

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Changing assumptions driving development of 6G as a GPT

From technology-centricity and service-centricity toward human-centricity.

The definition of mobile communications generations has evolved from technology-centric definitions toward service-centricity in 5G and toward human-centricity for 6G and beyond.

From technology push toward pull from social and environmental goals.

Up to 5G, the traditional innovation process in mobile communications can be characterized as a technology push from technology and equipment vendors toward operators and end-users. With 6G, new demands for social inclusivity or privacy, security, and safety up to national sovereignty, as well as environmental pressures, have raised triple bottom line sustainability to a driver for developing 6G as a general-purpose technology and an ecosystem-wide effort. This is also expected to continue in beyond 6G.

Changing assumptions driving development of 6G as a GPT

From international to national and local communications toward focal communications.

The provisioning of mobile communications services is changing from international and national operators' mass-produced and top-down offered services toward tailored local communications in 5G and 6G, e.g., with the help of softwarization, virtualization, cloudification, and network slicing. However, it is envisaged that in beyond 6G communications, focally provisioned bottom-up-built personalized on-demand services will emerge.

From quality of service and quality of experience toward immersion.

The utilization of mobile communications services has been by provisioning-defined quality of service or utilization-based quality of experience in up to 5G communications. In beyond 6G communications, immersive extended reality, holographic communications, and the metaverse(s) require novel types of quantification for the quality of utilization and experience

Changing assumptions driving development of 6G as a GPT

From ubiquitous connectivity toward ubiquitous intelligence.

With the convergence of artificial intelligence and other new capabilities like sensing with mobile communications, the assisting and automating role of these capabilities in up to 5G communications is expected to become augmenting in 6G, which means that the nature of communications will change from an availability challenge into what the degree of intelligence or other integrated capabilities available for use is.

From human–machine interfaces toward transhumanism.

The traditional device-based use of mobile communications in up to 5G networks is expected to change with new human–machine interfaces like virtual glasses or haptic communications in 6G. For beyond 6G communications, implanted sensors or devices enhance human capabilities and give rise to the emergence of transhumanism, the integration of humans and machines, but also new moral, ethical, and value-related concerns due to the presence of artificial intelligence

Business model innovation for GPT* mobile communications

*GPT = General Purpose Technology

5G Business models for MNOs

The General Bit-Pipe MNO business model is a future projection of today's dominant nation-wide MNO model with a large installed base who utilize a variety of mobile communication technologies from 2G to 5G, often complemented by Wi-Fi and IoT technologies to provide general mobile broadband connectivity to all in a mass-production bit-pipe mode. This business model can be used to offer public commercial networks or public commercial virtual network services.

The Segmented Specialized Service MNO business model builds on offering mobile connectivity bundled with specialized content to selected segments nation-wide or regionally. These operators are the challengers to dominant MNOs and have a smaller installed base and attempt to compete where the general bit-pipe operators are less competitive serving the long tail of customers through higher value-added services. This business model can be used to offer services such as public commercial networks, public commercial virtual networks, neutral hosts, or private local networks.

5G Business models for local networks

The Wholesale Service Local Operator business model builds on the opportunity to offer local hosted connectivity to MNOs' customers as a **neutral host**. This is an opportunity in public, but restricted places, such as campuses and hospitals where it is not feasible that all MNOs build their own network infrastructure but outsource it from a local operator. The local operator would then directly charge the MNOs, not the end users, for the service.

The Retail Service Local Operator business model is based on offering local connectivity and complementary data services to end users in venues such as shopping malls, hotels, or sharing workplaces/offices independent of MNOs. This business model may serve MNOs to provide private local networks or public network integrated non-public networks.

The Vertical Service Local Operator business model is about offering **private** local networks, i.e., connectivity, content, and context services for verticals like factories, campuses and ports independent of MNOs. The users of the service could be either humans or machines.

The Context Service Local Operator business model builds on offering **personalized** consumer services (via private local networks) or networks including connectivity and content and context data on-demand using, e.g., network slicing technology.

6G Business models for Incumbents

As an evolution of incumbent MNOs, the **6G MNO** business model will be building on end-to-end value chain **controlled** by the 6G MNO and supported by specialized firms tethered to the 6G MNO's connectivity-centered platform. This model will aim at monetizing interaction by '**matching**' the needs or '**bridging**' the customers via the **connectivity platform**. Automated network **slicing** will be used to offer differentiated service to segmented customer groups, private and public customers, and critical infrastructure providers. 6G MNOs are also expected to offer connectivity from a **multi-technology platform** that will consist of a selection of connectivity platforms that vary from low-earth-orbit, drone, and terrestrial 6G to hyper-local networks with a special focus on components and interfaces in the system. 6G MNOs will be **designed to serve the masses**, whether humans or machines. Additionally, 6G MNOs are envisioned to support the human and enterprise metaverses by providing the basic connectivity for them. For traditional MNOs, the **network neutrality principle** may constrain value capture in providing the long-tailed distribution of differentiated future services. They will rely on their existing infrastructure assets on top of which 6G will be built.

6G Business models for Incumbents

The **OTT operator** business model will build on **content** that the over-the top (OTT) service provider wants the end user to connect to. **Connectivity**, acquired from other types of operators, will be **bundled** as free or subsidized with content to provide a 'full service' that enables combined customer attraction and locked-in based value creation with a focus on maximizing demand to monetize content. Generally, OTT refers to digital service providers that **bypass** the traditional MNO's network to deliver audio, video, and other media over the Internet, utilizing the possibly revisited net-neutrality principles, affordably expanding their reach to the bottom four billion. In this model, the OTT operator as a platform owner builds on its' own **cloud** platform and content, leveraging connectivity from other types of operators, preferably from bit pipe operators, tailored for their needs, and will be able to benefit from its large customer base in 'bridging' between customers or 'sharing' contents mode. Any content that the complementors' offer can flexibly be added to platform-owning OTTs' offering in this model. Data and algorithms will play a central role in the functioning of this business model. OTT operators will focus on **human users** and are envisioned to be the consumer or enterprise metaverse providers.

6G Business models for Newcomers

The **edge operator** business model will build on the openness of ecosystems and **modularized** technology to provide tailored **localized or zone-specific connectivity, content, computing** (i.e., use the available hardware to process data), and context services, and in multiple locations or zones to scale the service. The key to understanding edge operators are their **context-specificity**. Depending on the type of customers and use cases they serve, they will develop specific sets of capabilities 'matching' customer needs and 'sharing' data or information between them while leveraging cloud infrastructure assets. Edge operators will drive the value chain in the **edge application context** and even create new revenue sources with hyper-local cloud infrastructure services with scalability, required availability, and **almost unlimited flexibility**. The diminishing value share of MNOs in edge cloud deals will trigger the number of private wireless deals of edge operators bypassing MNOs leveraging their infra-assets and creating a service layer to limit their value capture. Webscale born edge operators particularly are driving their successful transactional platform business model into **new/adjacent domains** where winning platforms cover innovation and transaction. The edge operators' business focus is on **organizations and communities** with either human or machine users. The edge operators may be expected to be the supporters of industrial metaverses.

6G Business models for Newcomers

The **telco broker** business model offers **connectivity or other resources or assets** needed for mobile services. It can be seen to emerge from specialized **data, artificial intelligence, and interface-control** based services in the converging **multi-platform ecosystem** of future 6G. The telco brokers lean on the additionality of disruptors, complementors, and specialized service providers in the multi-platform ecosystem to match and bridge the differing needs and resources together by ‘brokering.’ The key to understanding the telco brokers’ business model is the way they combine **algorithms**, ready-made **components** and existing resources, **interfaces**, and **data** residing in the multiplatform ecosystem for the needs of their customers. The telco brokers’ business focus may take many forms and is primarily defined by the needs of organizations and communities. Telco brokers may serve any kind of metaverses as a service enabler.

6G Business models for Disruptors

The **service-flow** business model **integrates focally** for the user, whether human or a machine—or a swarm of them—a set of on-demand services that the user needs **ubiquitously** regardless of location or connectivity provider. Future metaverses are examples of services requiring a service-flow business model in the background. The shift to cloud-based services has changed how enterprises purchase software and its development. Application developers have more control than before over what is being purchased. Companies build their products to make it **easy for developers** to adapt and shift their expensive top-down go-to-market motion to bottom-up product-led growth, where customers can easily try out the product and expand usage over time. A decentralized platform will distribute value between the players while open-source software will lower market entry barriers, promote interoperability, and expedite development cycles based on shared knowledge. These service-flow business models may require enhanced privacy and security via integrated **trust-services**, specified network capabilities and resources, specialized human-machine interfaces that replace traditional devices or equipment, and advanced AI capabilities. The service-flow business model will disrupt the other envisioned 6G-enabled mobile operator business models by shifting the focus from platform and infrastructure-centric offerings to **human-centric service demand**.

Toward multiplatforms in 6G

Vertical supply side Incumbent connectivity platforms

Horizontal demand side adjacent & content platforms

Multisided & multilayered newborn commerce platforms

Commerce
Context
Content
Cloud
Connectivity

○ Service provider ---▶ Service provider expansion direction ● Specialized services ■ Complementary services

Role of regulation...?

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